

A Preliminary Floristic Exploration in Sacred Maha Kshetram Hill (Tohadri), Mangalgiri, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract

Sacred groves in Andhra Pradesh are known as Pavithravanas. A total number of 730 sacred groves have been documented till date. These Pavithravanas or sacred groves are dedicated to various local deities and also to Hindu gods and goddesses. Some of the deities to whom the sacred groves are dedicated are Shiva, Rudrakoteswara, Hanuman, Saraswathi, Thimmaraya Swamy, Gangamma, Nagadevatha, Chennakesava, Narasimha and Akkamma (WWF Andhra Pradesh, 1996). During study of sacred grove of Andhra Pradesh State, India various field trips were conducted and were GIS Photographic from various natural populations during the period 2013-2025. Sacred groves identifications activities data and plants specimens collected flowering or fruiting seasons. Specimens critically observed and identified. In the present study, a total of 521 wild and naturalized species were recorded from Mangalgiri Panakala Narasimha Swamy Hills, Guntur District. These 521 Species were recorded from Mangalgiri Panakala Narasimha Swamy Hills, Andhra Pradesh. These 521 wild and naturalized taxa belong to 310 genera and 78 families. Of the 521 wild and naturalized species, 103 trees, 78 shrubs; 294 herbs; 42 Climbers and remaining 4 species Liana. Sacred groves in Andhra Pradesh are deteriorating at an alarming rate due to changes in religious beliefs and developmental pressure. Many temples associated with sacred groves have been modernized by removing the vegetation. Some of the species commonly found in the sacred groves of Andhra Pradesh are black plum, tamarind, mango, jackfruit, neem, beechwood and pipal. Some of the species have unique abilities such as nitrogen fixation etc. Such Species are variously known as keystone species or functional groups.

Keywords: *Mangalgiri, Panakala Narasimha Swamy Temple, Primary Data Collections, Maha Kshetram.*

Suggested citation: Suneeta, D., Skylab, G., Rao, V.M.M., & Ikkurthi, V.K. (2025). A Preliminary Floristic Exploration in Sacred Maha Kshetram Hill (Tohadri), Mangalgiri, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(12), 103-124. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2025.2(12).06

Introduction

The sacred groves are important repositories of floral and faunal diversity that have been conserved by local communities in a sustainable manner. They are often the last refuge of endemic species in the geographical region. The role of cultural and spiritual values is crucial to nature conservation. In India, the sacred groves are still in the process of being documented. There are 13,270 sacred groves that are found to intact. Out of this only 138 hectares comprise of totally undisturbed vegetation and about 3188 hectares have an open canopy. However, initial studies indicate that the number of sacred groves in the country may be as high as 100,000 to 150,000 (Malhotra, 1998). The total area under sacred groves in India has been estimated to be 33,000 hectares which comes to 0.01 percent of the total area of the country. However, the actual area could be as high as 42000 hectares considering the 4,445 sacred groves reported so far (Gokhale et al. 1998). However, in contrast to the above facts, C.P.R. Environmental Education Centre has so far documented a total of 10,377 sacred groves which have been authenticated. In India, over 1 million Sacred Forests and 100,000 to 150,000 sacred groves exist. This spiritual belief is very similar to the mechanism of a healthy ecosystem (Miryala, et al., 2025).

Many scientists believe that traditions and faiths like these are essential to encourage biodiversity conservation efforts (Malhotra et al. 1998). A document of (MAB 1995) has described the sacred groves present in Ghana, Senegal, and Sumatra. Various sacred sites associated with rich vegetation in Bangladesh were reported by (Hussain 1998). All forms of vegetation in the groves are supposed to be under the protection of reigning deity of that grove, and the removal of even a small twig is a taboo (Vartak and Gadgil 1973). Collection and removal of any material from the sacred groves is prohibited (Khan et al. 1987; Khiewtam and Ramakrishnan 1989). Sacred groves are found all over India especially in those regions where indigenous communities inhabit. Traced the historical link of sacred groves with the pre-agricultural, hunting and gathering stage, before human being had settled down to raise livestock or till land (Gadgil and Vartak 1976, 1981 a,b). Most of the sacred groves reported from India are in the Western Ghats, North Eastern India and Central India (Gadgil and Vartak 1976; Burman 1992; Rodgers 1994; Balasuramanyam and Induchoodan 1996; Tripathi 2006; Khumbongmayum et al. 2005). In India sacred groves are found mainly in tribal dominated areas and known by different names in ethnic terms (Bhakat 1990) such as Sarna or Dev in Madhya Pradesh, Devrai or Deovani in Maharashtra, Sarnas in Bihar, Oran's in Rajasthan, Devaravana or Devarakadu in Karnataka, Sarpakavu and Kavuvu in Tamil Nadu and Kerala, Dev van in Himachal Pradesh, Law Lyngdoh or Law Kyntang etc. in Meghalaya, Sarana or Jaherthan in Jharkhand and Laiumang in Manipur (Miryala, et al., 2025).

Materials and Methods

During study of sacred grove of Andhra Pradesh State, India various field trips were conducted and were vouched from various natural populations during the period 2013-2024. Collected Sacred groves identifications activities data and plants photographic data collected flowering or fruiting seasons. Plants critically observed and identified. Based on the information, plants were identified with the help of local floras and confirmed by comparing with authenticated specimens in Deccan Regional Centre, BSI, Hyderabad, Coimbatore and central National herbarium (CAL), Calcutta. The state of Andhra Pradesh, alone, has over 500 sacred groves (Anon. 1996), Locally known as Pavithravanalu (Rao et al. 2001; Sunitha and Rao 1999) studied the characteristics and distribution of the flora of the sacred groves in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. (Prasad Varma et. al. 2023) reported a total of 67 species 57 genera and 32 families in Bodakondamma sacred grove, Eastern Ghats, Visakhapatnam District. Biodiversity of Sacred groves is preserved in mostly undisturbed condition probably due to certain taboos and religious beliefs (Lakshmi Narayana and Venkaiah

1998). The Local people of each sacred grove in general also believe that their livelihood, security and cultural existence are complementary to the blessings of their deity. Perusal of related published literature (Gamble 1915; Gamble and Fischer 1915; Gibbs 1974; Halbar 1986; Hooker 1984; Hooker 1872-1897; Jain 1964; Jain and Rao 1977; Jain 1981; Jain 1964; Jain 1981; Kirtikar and Boser 1933; Nadkarni 1976; Pullaiah and Yasodamma 1989; Pullaiah and Chennaiah 1997; Rao and Sree Ramulu 1986; Reddy et al. 1986; Subba Rao and Kumari 2002-2008) for the taxonomic confirmation.

Results and Discussions

In the present study, a total of 521 Species were recorded from Maha Kshetram, Mangalgi, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh. These 521 wild and naturalized taxa belong to 310 genera and 78 families, the latter taxa identified following APG IV Classification. Of the 521 taxa are identified through 2025 herbarium specimens made in the present study based on published records; of the latter. Descriptions arranged Family wise Chronological (A-Z) order. Abstract of major group-wise analysis of families, genera and species and infra-specific vascular plant taxa is as follows:

They serve as biodiversity hotspots, conserving rare and endemic species of flora and fauna. Ecologically, they act as carbon sinks, regulate microclimates, and prevent soil erosion. Culturally, they are integral to local traditions, often protected through religious beliefs, rituals, and taboos (Miriyala, et al., 2025). They also support traditional knowledge systems, including medicinal plant usage. Despite their importance, sacred groves face threats like deforestation and urbanization, highlighting the need for conservation efforts that integrate local communities and modern ecological strategies. Floristic exploration of sacred groves is a vital activity for understanding and conserving plant biodiversity.

Conclusion

Sacred groves are unique ecosystems, often serving as reservoirs of rare, endemic, and medicinal plant species. Here are the key reasons why floristic exploration is crucial. Sacred groves are biodiversity hotspots. Floristic exploration helps identify and catalogue plant species, including those that are rare, endangered, or have limited geographical distribution. Trees and plants in sacred groves play a significant role in carbon capture. Identifying dominant species helps estimate their carbon storage potential. Plants in sacred groves often exhibit resilience to climate extremes. Exploring their floristic composition can provide insights into climate-adaptive species. Floristic surveys can reveal the impact of deforestation, grazing, and urbanization on plant diversity, emphasizing the need for conservation. Identifying invasive plant species helps manage threats to native flora. Floristic exploration in sacred groves is not just a scientific endeavour but also a conservation imperative. It integrates traditional knowledge with modern science, ensuring that these ancient ecological sanctuaries continue to thrive and provide their invaluable benefits to nature and society.

Acknowledgements

The authors greatly acknowledge Andhra Pradesh State Forest Department for providing permission. We are also thankful to Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change for facilities and to Department of Environment and Forests, Andhra Pradesh, for necessary permission and logistic support in during field studies.

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Appendix

Table 1. Plant Species Check List- Provided A-Z Families Wise

S. No	Name of the Species	Families-APG-IV	Habit
1	<i>Andrographis serpyllifolia</i> (Rottl. ex Vahl.) Wt.	Acanthaceae	H
2	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
3	<i>Barleria cristata</i> L.	Acanthaceae	S
4	<i>Barleria noctiflora</i> L.f.	Acanthaceae	S
5	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.	Acanthaceae	S
6	<i>Blepharis integrifolia</i> (L.f.) E.Mey. & Drège ex Schinz	Acanthaceae	H
7	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i> (L.) B.Heyne ex Roth	Acanthaceae	H
8	<i>Crossandra infundibuliformis</i> (L.) Nees	Acanthaceae	S
9	<i>Dicliptera paniculata</i> (Forssk.) I.Darbysh	Acanthaceae	H
10	<i>Dipteracanthus prostratus</i> (Poir.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
11	<i>Ecboium viride</i> (Forssk.) Alston	Acanthaceae	H
12	<i>Elytraria acaulis</i> (L.f.) Lindau	Acanthaceae	H
13	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i> (Schumach.) Heine	Acanthaceae	H
14	<i>Indonesiella echioides</i> (L.) Sreem.	Acanthaceae	H
15	<i>Justicia glauca</i> Rottler	Acanthaceae	H
16	<i>Justicia procumbens</i> L.	Acanthaceae	H
17	<i>Lepidagathis cristata</i> Willd.	Acanthaceae	H
18	<i>Rostellularia prostrata</i> (C.B.Clarke) R.B.Majumdar	Acanthaceae	H
19	<i>Ruellia patula</i> Jacq	Acanthaceae	H
20	<i>Rungia pectinata</i> (L.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
21	<i>Rungia repens</i> (L.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
22	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	Aizoaceae	H
23	<i>Trianthema triquetra</i> Rottler & Willd.	Aizoaceae	H
24	<i>Zaleya decandra</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Aizoaceae	H
25	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
26	<i>Aerva javanica</i> (Burm.f.) Juss. ex Schult.	Amaranthaceae	H
27	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	Amaranthaceae	H
28	<i>Allmania nodiflora</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Wight	Amaranthaceae	H
29	<i>Alternanthera pungens</i> Kunth	Amaranthaceae	H
30	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R.Br. ex DC.	Amaranthaceae	H
31	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
32	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
33	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
34	<i>Digera muricata</i> (L.) Mart.	Amaranthaceae	H
35	<i>Gomphrena serrata</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
36	<i>Pupalia lappacea</i> (L.) Juss.	Amaranthaceae	H
37	<i>Trichuriella monsoniae</i> (L. f.) Bennet	Amaranthaceae	H
38	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i> (Houtt.) Merr	Anacardiaceae	T
39	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Annonaceae	T
40	<i>Polyalthia cerasoides</i> (Roxb.) Bedd.	Annonaceae	T
41	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) Dryand.	Apocyanaceae	S
42	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Aiton) Dryand.	Apocyanaceae	S
43	<i>Caralluma adscendens</i> (Roxb.) R.Br.	Apocyanaceae	H
44	<i>Caralluma umbellata</i> Haw.	Apocyanaceae	H
45	<i>Carissa carandas</i> L.	Apocyanaceae	S
46	<i>Catharanthus pusillus</i> (Murray) G.Don	Apocyanaceae	H
47	<i>Ceropegia juncea</i> Roxb	Apocyanaceae	H
48	<i>Cryptostegia grandiflora</i> Roxb. ex R.Br.	Apocyanaceae	C
49	<i>Decalepis hamiltonii</i> Wight & Arn.	Apocyanaceae	C
50	<i>Dregea volubilis</i> (L.f.) Benth. ex Hook.f.	Apocyanaceae	C
51	<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> (Retz.) R.Br. ex Sm.	Apocyanaceae	C

52	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Schult.	Apocyanaceae	H
53	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> var. <i>pubescens</i> Hook.f	Apocyanaceae	H
54	<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i> (L.) W.T.Aiton	Apocyanaceae	S
55	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> (Retz.) Wight & Arn	Apocyanaceae	S
56	<i>Oxystelma esculentum</i> (L. f.) Sm.	Apocyanaceae	L
57	<i>Pentatropis capensis</i> (L. f.) Bullock	Apocyanaceae	Twin
58	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	Apocyanaceae	C
59	<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Apocyanaceae	Twin
60	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> R.Br.	Apocyanaceae	T
61	<i>Aponogeton crispus</i> Thunb	Aponogetonaceae	H
62	<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	Araceae	Aq,H
63	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Arecaceae	T
64	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb	Arecaceae	T
65	<i>Aristolochia bracteata</i>	Aristolochiaceae	H
66	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L.	Aristolochiaceae	Twin
67	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Asparagaceae	C
68	<i>Drimia indica</i> (Roxb.) Jessop	Asparagaceae	H
69	<i>Ledebouria revoluta</i> (L.f.) Jessop	Asparagaceae	H
70	<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> DC	Asteraceae	H
71	<i>Bidens bipinnata</i> L.	Asteraceae	H
72	<i>Blainvillea acmella</i> (L.) Philipson	Asteraceae	H
73	<i>Blumea bifoliata</i> (L.) DC	Asteraceae	H
74	<i>Blumea eriantha</i> DC	Asteraceae	H
75	<i>Blumea obliqua</i> (L.) Druce	Asteraceae	H
76	<i>Cyanthillium cinereum</i> (L.) H.Rob	Asteraceae	H
77	<i>Dicoma tomentosa</i> Cass.	Asteraceae	H
78	<i>Echinops echinatus</i> Roxb	Asteraceae	H
79	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	H
80	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> (L.) DC. ex DC.	Asteraceae	H
81	<i>Glossocardia bosvallia</i> (L.f.) DC	Asteraceae	H
82	<i>Lagascea mollis</i> Cav.	Asteraceae	H
83	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Asteraceae	H
84	<i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling	Asteraceae	H
85	<i>Pulicaria wightiana</i> (DC.) C.B.Clarke	Asteraceae	H
86	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	Asteraceae	H
87	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	H
88	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Asteraceae	S
89	<i>Impatiens balsamina</i> L.	Balsaminaceae	H
90	<i>Dolichandrone falcata</i> (Wall. ex DC.) Seem	Bignoniaceae	T
91	<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kunth	Bignoniaceae	S
92	<i>Cochlospermum religiosum</i> (L.) Alston	Bixaceae	T
93	<i>Coldenia procumbens</i> L.	Boraginaceae	H
94	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G.Forst.	Boraginaceae	T

95	<i>Cordia monoica</i> Roxb.	Boraginaceae	T
96	<i>Ehretia microphylla</i> Lam	Boraginaceae	T
97	<i>Heliotropium bracteatum</i> R.Br.	Boraginaceae	H
98	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L.	Boraginaceae	H
99	<i>Heliotropium scabrum</i> Retz.	Boraginaceae	H
100	<i>Heliotropium strigosum</i> Willd.	Boraginaceae	H
101	<i>Heliotropium zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) Lam.	Boraginaceae	H
102	<i>Rotula aquatica</i> Lour.	Boraginaceae	H
103	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) Lehm.	Boraginaceae	H
104	<i>Trichodesma zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) R.Br	Boraginaceae	H
105	<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb. ex Colebr	Burseraceae	T
106	<i>Commiphora berryi</i> (Arn.) Engl.	Burseraceae	T
107	<i>Commiphora caudata</i> (Wight & Arn.) Engl	Burseraceae	T
108	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> Roxb	Burseraceae	T
109	<i>Opuntia stricta</i> (Haw.) Haw.	Cactaceae	S
110	<i>Cadaba fruticosa</i> (L.) Druce	Capparaceae	S
111	<i>Capparis brevispina</i> DC	Capparaceae	S
112	<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forssk.) Edgew	Capparaceae	S
113	<i>Capparis divaricata</i> Lam	Capparaceae	T
114	<i>Capparis floribunda</i> Lepr. ex Walp	Capparaceae	S
115	<i>Capparis grandis</i> L.f.	Capparaceae	T
116	<i>Capparis sepiaria</i> L	Capparaceae	S
117	<i>Capparis zeylanica</i> L	Capparaceae	S
118	<i>Crateva religiosa</i> G. Forst.	Capparaceae	T
119	<i>Maerua apetala</i> (Spreng.) M. Jacobs	Capparaceae	S
120	<i>Maerua oblongifolia</i> (Forssk.) A.Rich	Capparaceae	S
121	<i>Polycarpaea aurea</i> Wight & Arn.	Caryophyllaceae	H
122	<i>Polycarpaea corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam	Caryophyllaceae	H
123	<i>Cassine glauca</i> (Rottb.) Kuntze	Celastraceae	T
124	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i> Willd	Celastraceae	C
125	<i>Gymnosporia emarginata</i> (Willd.) Thwaites	Celastraceae	S
126	<i>Cleome aspera</i> J.Koenig ex DC.	Cleomaceae	H
127	<i>Cleome felina</i> L.f.	Cleomaceae	H
128	<i>Cleome gynandra</i> L.	Cleomaceae	H
129	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Cleomaceae	H
130	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Colchicaceae	C
131	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wall. ex Guillem. & Perr.	Combretaceae	T
132	<i>Combretum albidum</i> G.Don	Combretaceae	S
133	<i>Getonia floribunda</i> Roxb	Combretaceae	L
134	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wight & Arn	Combretaceae	T
135	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Combretaceae	T
136	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Combretaceae	T
137	<i>Commelina attenuata</i> K.D.Koenig ex Vahl	Commelinaceae	H

138	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Commelinaceae	H
139	<i>Commelina clavata</i> C.B.Clarke	Commelinaceae	H
140	<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm.f.	Commelinaceae	H
141	<i>Commelina ensifolia</i> R.Br.	Commelinaceae	H
142	<i>Commelina erecta</i> L.	Commelinaceae	H
143	<i>Commelina longifolia</i> Lam.	Commelinaceae	H
144	<i>Commelina paludosa</i> Blume	Commelinaceae	H
145	<i>Cyanotis axillaris</i> (L.) D.Don ex Sweet	Commelinaceae	H
146	<i>Cyanotis cucullata</i> (Roth) Kunth	Commelinaceae	H
147	<i>Cyanotis fasciculata</i> (B.Heyne ex Roth) Schult. & Schult.f.	Commelinaceae	H
148	<i>Cyanotis tuberosa</i> (Roxb.) Schult. & Schult.f.	Commelinaceae	H
149	<i>Murdannia spirata</i> (L.) G.Brückn.	Commelinaceae	H
150	<i>Argyrea cymosa</i> Sweet	Convolvulaceae	C
151	<i>Cuscuta chinensis</i> Lam.	Convolvulaceae	C
152	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (L.) L.	Convolvulaceae	H
153	<i>Ipomoea coptica</i> (L.) Roth ex Roem. & Schult.	Convolvulaceae	C
154	<i>Ipomoea hederifolia</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	C
155	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) Ker Gawl.	Convolvulaceae	C
156	<i>Ipomoea pes-tigridis</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	C
157	<i>Ipomoea staphylina</i> Roem. & Schult.	Convolvulaceae	C
158	<i>Merremia aegyptia</i> (L.) Urb	Convolvulaceae	C
159	<i>Merremia gangetica</i> Cufod.	Convolvulaceae	C
160	<i>Merremia tridentata</i> (L.) Hallier f.	Convolvulaceae	C
161	<i>Operculina turpethum</i> (L.) Silva Manso	Convolvulaceae	C
162	<i>Rivea hypocrateriformis</i> Choisy	Convolvulaceae	C
163	<i>Alangium salviifolium</i> (L.f.) Wangerin	Cornaceae	S
164	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt	Cucurbitaceae	C
165	<i>Corallocarpus epigaeus</i> (Rottler) Hook.f.	Cucurbitaceae	C
166	<i>Ctenolepis garcini</i> (L.) C.B.Clarke	Cucurbitaceae	C
167	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C.Jeffrey	Cucurbitaceae	C
168	<i>Mukia maderaspatana</i> (L.) M.Roem.	Cucurbitaceae	C
169	<i>Bulbostylis barbata</i> (Rottb.) C.B.Clarke	Cyperaceae	C
170	<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	H
171	<i>Cyperus laevigatus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	H
172	<i>Cyperus nutans</i> Vahl	Cyperaceae	H
173	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	H
174	<i>Cyperus rubicundus</i> Vahl	Cyperaceae	H
175	<i>Eleocharis atropurpurea</i> (Retz.) J.Presl & C.Presl	Cyperaceae	H
176	<i>Fimbristylis cymosa</i> R.Br.	Cyperaceae	H
177	<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	H
178	<i>Fimbristylis falcata</i> (Vahl) Kunth	Cyperaceae	H
179	<i>Fimbristylis quinqueangularis</i> (Vahl) Kunth	Cyperaceae	H

180	<i>Kyllinga bulbosa</i> P.Beauv.	Cyperaceae	H
181	<i>Kyllinga nemoralis</i> (J.R.Forst. & G.Forst.) Dandy ex Hutch. & Dalziel	Cyperaceae	H
182	<i>Pycneus flavidus</i> (Retz.) T.Koyama	Cyperaceae	H
183	<i>Diospyros chloroxylon</i> Roxb.	Ebenaceae	S
184	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i> Roxb.	Ebenaceae	T
185	<i>Diospyros vera</i> (Lour.) A.Chev	Ebenaceae	T
186	<i>Erythroxyllum monogynum</i> Roxb	Erythroxyllaceae	S
187	<i>Acalypha alnifolia</i> Klein ex Willd.	Euphorbiaceae	S
188	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	H
189	<i>Acalypha lanceolata</i> Willd.	Euphorbiaceae	H
190	<i>Acalypha malabarica</i> Müll.Arg	Euphorbiaceae	H
191	<i>Chrozophora rottleri</i> (Geiseler) A.Juss. ex Spreng	Euphorbiaceae	H
192	<i>Croton bonplandianus</i> Baill.	Euphorbiaceae	H
193	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	T
194	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	H
195	<i>Euphorbia heyneana</i> Spreng	Euphorbiaceae	H
196	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	H
197	<i>Euphorbia indica</i> Lam.	Euphorbiaceae	H
198	<i>Givotia moluccana</i> (L.) Sreem.	Euphorbiaceae	T
199	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	S
200	<i>Micrococca mercurialis</i> (L.) Benth	Euphorbiaceae	H
201	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Fabaceae	C
202	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> Benth	Fabaceae	T
203	<i>Acacia caesia</i> (L.) Willd.	Fabaceae	S
204	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.f.) Willd.	Fabaceae	T
205	<i>Acacia chundra</i> (Rottler) Willd	Fabaceae	T
206	<i>Acacia farnesiana</i> (L.) Willd.	Fabaceae	T
207	<i>Acacia ferruginea</i> DC	Fabaceae	T
208	<i>Acacia horrida</i> (L.) Willd.	Fabaceae	T
209	<i>Acacia leucophloea</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Fabaceae	T
210	<i>Acacia torta</i> (Roxb.) Craib	Fabaceae	S
211	<i>Aeschynomene indica</i> L.	Fabaceae	H
212	<i>Albizia amara</i> (Roxb.) B.Boivin	Fabaceae	T
213	<i>Albizia odoratissima</i> (L.f.) Benth.	Fabaceae	T
214	<i>Alysicarpus hamosus</i> Edgew.	Fabaceae	H
215	<i>Alysicarpus heterophyllus</i> (Baker) Jafri & Ali	Fabaceae	H
216	<i>Alysicarpus longifolius</i> (Spreng.) Wight & Arn	Fabaceae	H
217	<i>Alysicarpus monilifer</i> (L.) DC	Fabaceae	H
218	<i>Alysicarpus scariosus</i> (Spreng.) Thwaites	Fabaceae	H
219	<i>Alysicarpus vaginalis</i> (L.) DC	Fabaceae	H
220	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> L.	Fabaceae	T
221	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	Fabaceae	T
222	<i>Bauhinia tomentosa</i> L.	Fabaceae	T

223	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub	Fabaceae	T
224	<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i> (L.) Roxb.	Fabaceae	S
225	<i>Caesalpinia coriaria</i> (Jacq.) Willd	Fabaceae	T
226	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i> (L.) Thouars	Fabaceae	C
227	<i>Canavalia gladiata</i> (Jacq.) DC	Fabaceae	V
228	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Fabaceae	T
229	<i>Chamaecrista absus</i> (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	Fabaceae	H
230	<i>Chamaecrista kleinii</i> (Wight & Arn.) V.Singh	Fabaceae	H
231	<i>Chamaecrista pumila</i> (Lam.) K.Larsen	Fabaceae	H
232	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L	Fabaceae	C
233	<i>Crotalaria albida</i> Roth	Fabaceae	H
234	<i>Crotalaria bifaria</i> L.f.	Fabaceae	H
235	<i>Crotalaria hebecarpa</i> (DC.) Rudd	Fabaceae	H
236	<i>Crotalaria hirsuta</i> Willd	Fabaceae	H
237	<i>Crotalaria medicaginea</i> Lam	Fabaceae	H
238	<i>Crotalaria mysorensis</i> Roth	Fabaceae	H
239	<i>Crotalaria pulchra</i> Andrews	Fabaceae	S
240	<i>Crotalaria ramosissima</i> Roxb	Fabaceae	H
241	<i>Crotalaria retusa</i> L.	Fabaceae	H
242	<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i> L	Fabaceae	H
243	<i>Dalbergia lanceolaria</i> L.f.	Fabaceae	T
244	<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> Roxb	Fabaceae	T
245	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> DC.	Fabaceae	T
246	<i>Derris scandens</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Fabaceae	C
247	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	H
248	<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	H
249	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	Fabaceae	S
250	<i>Erythrina stricta</i> Roxb.	Fabaceae	T
251	<i>Galactia tenuiflora</i> (Willd.) Wight & Arn.	Fabaceae	C
252	<i>Hardwickia binata</i> Roxb	Fabaceae	T
253	<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i> L.	Fabaceae	S
254	<i>Indigofera linifolia</i> (L.f.) Retz.	Fabaceae	H
255	<i>Indigofera linnaei</i> Ali	Fabaceae	H
256	<i>Indigofera prostrata</i> Willd.	Fabaceae	H
257	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> L.	Fabaceae	S
258	<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i> L.	Fabaceae	S
259	<i>Indigofera trita</i> L.f.	Fabaceae	S
260	<i>Mimosa hamata</i> Willd	Fabaceae	S
261	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	Fabaceae	H
262	<i>Mundulea sericea</i> (Willd.) A.Chev.	Fabaceae	T
263	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth	Fabaceae	T
264	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Fabaceae	T
265	<i>Prosopis chilensis</i> (Molina) Stuntz	Fabaceae	T

266	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce	Fabaceae	T
267	<i>Pseudarthria viscida</i> (L.) Wight & Arn	Fabaceae	H
268	<i>Rhynchosia capitata</i> (Roth) DC	Fabaceae	C
269	<i>Rhynchosia heynei</i> Wight & Arn	Fabaceae	C
270	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	H
271	<i>Senna auriculata</i> (L.) Roxb	Fabaceae	S
272	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	Fabaceae	S
273	<i>Senna tora</i> (L.) Roxb	Fabaceae	H
274	<i>Sesbania bispinosa</i> (Jacq.) W.Wight	Fabaceae	S
275	<i>Sesbania procumbens</i> (Roxb.) Wight & Arn	Fabaceae	H
276	<i>Smithia conferta</i> Sm	Fabaceae	H
277	<i>Stylosanthes fruticosa</i> (Retz.) Alston	Fabaceae	H
278	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Fabaceae	T
279	<i>Tephrosia maxima</i> (L.) Pers	Fabaceae	H
280	<i>Tephrosia pumila</i> (Lam.) Pers.	Fabaceae	H
281	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.) Pers.	Fabaceae	H
282	<i>Tephrosia strigosa</i> (Dalzell) Santapau & Maheshw.	Fabaceae	H
283	<i>Tephrosia villosa</i> (L.) Pers.	Fabaceae	H
284	<i>Vigna aconitifolia</i> (Jacq.) Marechal	Fabaceae	H
285	<i>Vigna trilobata</i> (L.) Verdc.	Fabaceae	H
286	<i>Zornia gibbosa</i> Span.	Fabaceae	H
287	<i>Canscora diffusa</i> (Vahl) R.Br. ex Roem. & Schult	Gentianaceae	H
288	<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Poir. ex Lam.) A.Raynal	Gentianaceae	H
289	<i>Hoppea dichotoma</i> Willd.	Gentianaceae	H
290	<i>Gisekia pharnaceoides</i> L.	Gisekiaceae	H
291	<i>Gyrocarpus americanus</i> Jacq.	Hernandiaceae	T
292	<i>Anisochilus carnosus</i> (L.f.) Wall.	Lamiaceae	H
293	<i>Anisomeles indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Lamiaceae	H
294	<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Sims	Lamiaceae	H
295	<i>Gmelina asiatica</i> L.	Lamiaceae	T
296	<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.) Poit	Lamiaceae	H
297	<i>Leonotis nepetifolia</i> (L.) R.Br.	Lamiaceae	H
298	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link	Lamiaceae	H
299	<i>Leucas biflora</i> (Vahl) Sm.	Lamiaceae	H
300	<i>Leucas diffusa</i> Benth	Lamiaceae	H
301	<i>Leucas stricta</i> Benth.	Lamiaceae	H
302	<i>Ocimum americanum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	H
303	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	H
304	<i>Orthosiphon rubicundus</i> (D.Don) Benth.	Lamiaceae	H
305	<i>Premna mollissima</i> Roth	Lamiaceae	S
306	<i>Premna tomentosa</i> Willd.	Lamiaceae	T
307	<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Lamiaceae	S
308	<i>Cassytha filiformis</i> L.	Lauraceae	C

309	<i>Hugonia serrata</i> Lam.	Linaceae	S
310	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.	Loganiaceae	T
311	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i> L.f.	Loganiaceae	T
312	<i>Corbichonia decumbens</i> (Forssk.) Exell	Lophiocarpaceae	H
313	<i>Dendrophthoe falcata</i> (L.f.) Ettingsh.	Loranthaceae	S
314	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	H
315	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i> (L.) Kurz	Lythraceae	S
316	<i>Hiptage benghalensis</i> (L.) Kurz	Malpighiaceae	C
317	<i>Abelmoschus ficulneus</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	Malvaceae	H
318	<i>Abutilon hirtum</i> (Lam.) Sweet	Malvaceae	S
319	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Malvaceae	S
320	<i>Abutilon pannosum</i> (G.Forst.) Schldtl	Malvaceae	S
321	<i>Corchorus aestuans</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
322	<i>Corchorus fascicularis</i> Lam	Malvaceae	S
323	<i>Corchorus olitorius</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
324	<i>Corchorus trilocularis</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
325	<i>Corchorus urticifolius</i> Wight & Arn.	Malvaceae	H
326	<i>Firmiana simplex</i> (L.) W.Wight	Malvaceae	T
327	<i>Grewia bracteata</i> Roth	Malvaceae	S
328	<i>Grewia damine</i> Gaertn	Malvaceae	T
329	<i>Grewia hirsuta</i> Vahl	Malvaceae	S
330	<i>Grewia orbiculata</i> Rottler	Malvaceae	T
331	<i>Grewia tenax</i> (Forssk.) Fiori	Malvaceae	S
332	<i>Grewia tiliifolia</i> Vahl	Malvaceae	T
333	<i>Grewia villosa</i> Willd	Malvaceae	S
334	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Malvaceae	T
335	<i>Hibiscus lobatus</i> (Murray) Kuntze	Malvaceae	S
336	<i>Hibiscus micranthus</i> L.f.	Malvaceae	H
337	<i>Hibiscus panduriformis</i> Burm.f.	Malvaceae	S
338	<i>Hibiscus vitifolius</i> L.	Malvaceae	S
339	<i>Malachra capitata</i> (L.) L.	Malvaceae	H
340	<i>Malvastrum coromandelianum</i> (L.) Garcke	Malvaceae	H
341	<i>Melhania incana</i> B.Heyne ex Wall.	Malvaceae	H
342	<i>Melochia corchorifolia</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
343	<i>Pavonia zeylanica</i> (L.) Cav	Malvaceae	H
344	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	Malvaceae	H
345	<i>Sida cordata</i> (Burm.f.) Borss.Waalk	Malvaceae	H
346	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
347	<i>Sida mysorensis</i> Wight & Arn	Malvaceae	H
348	<i>Sida ovata</i> Forssk.	Malvaceae	H
349	<i>Sida rhombifolia</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
350	<i>Sida spinosa</i> L.	Malvaceae	H

351	<i>Thespesia populnea</i> (L.) Sol. ex Corrêa	Malvaceae	T
352	<i>Triumfetta pentandra</i> A.Rich	Malvaceae	H
353	<i>Triumfetta rhomboidea</i> Jacq	Malvaceae	H
354	<i>Triumfetta rotundifolia</i> Lam	Malvaceae	H
355	<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
356	<i>Waltheria indica</i> L.	Malvaceae	S
357	<i>Martynia annua</i> L.	Martyniaceae	H
358	<i>Memecylon umbellatum</i> Burm. f.	Melastomataceae	T
359	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss	Meliaceae	T
360	<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	Meliaceae	T
361	<i>Soymida febrifuga</i> (Roxb.) A. Juss	Meliaceae	T
362	<i>Swietenia mahagoni</i> (L.) Jacq.	Meliaceae	T
363	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Menispermaceae	V
364	<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> (L.) W.Theob.	Menispermaceae	C
365	<i>Tiliacora racemosa</i> Colebr. (= <i>T. acuminata</i> Miers)	Menispermaceae	C
366	<i>Tinospora sinensis</i> (Lour.) Merr. (= <i>T. cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers)	Menispermaceae	V
367	<i>Glinus lotoides</i> L.	Molluginaceae	H
368	<i>Glinus oppositifolius</i> (L.) Aug.DC.	Molluginaceae	H
369	<i>Mollugo nudicaulis</i> Lam	Molluginaceae	H
370	<i>Mollugo pentaphylla</i> L.	Molluginaceae	H
371	<i>Ficus amplissima</i> Sm.	Moraceae	T
372	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Moraceae	T
373	<i>Ficus hispida</i> L.f.	Moraceae	T
374	<i>Ficus mollis</i> Vahl	Moraceae	T
375	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Moraceae	T
376	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Moraceae	T
377	<i>Streblus asper</i> Lour	Moraceae	T
378	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	T
379	<i>Boerhavia chinensis</i> (L.) Rottb	Nyctaginaceae	H
380	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	H
381	<i>Boerhavia erecta</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	H
382	<i>Ochna lanceolata</i> Kuntze	Ochnaceae	T
383	<i>Ochna obtusata</i> DC.	Ochnaceae	T
384	<i>Olax scandens</i> Roxb.	Olacaceae	S
385	<i>Jasminum auriculatum</i> Vahl	Oleaceae	S
386	<i>Cansjera rheedii</i> Blanco	Opiliaceae	L
387	<i>Opilia amentacea</i> Roxb	Opiliaceae	L
388	<i>Striga angustifolia</i> (D. Don) C.J. Saldanha	Orobanchaceae	H
389	<i>Striga asiatica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Orobanchaceae	H
390	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	H
391	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Papaveraceae	H
392	<i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	Passifloraceae	V

393	<i>Pedaliium murex</i> L.	Pedaliaceae	H
394	<i>Bridelia montana</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Phyllanthaceae	T
395	<i>Cleistanthus collinus</i> (Roxb.) Benth. ex Hook.f.	Phyllanthaceae	T
396	<i>Flueggea leucopyrus</i> Willd.	Phyllanthaceae	S
397	<i>Flueggea virosa</i> (Roxb. ex Willd.) Royle	Phyllanthaceae	S
398	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schumach. & Thonn.	Phyllanthaceae	H
399	<i>Phyllanthus debilis</i> Klein ex Willd.	Phyllanthaceae	H
400	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	T
401	<i>Phyllanthus maderaspatensis</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	H
402	<i>Phyllanthus pinnatus</i> (Wight) G.L.Webster	Phyllanthaceae	S
403	<i>Phyllanthus reticulatus</i> Poir.	Phyllanthaceae	S
404	<i>Phyllanthus virgatus</i> G.Forst.	Phyllanthaceae	H
405	<i>Tragia involucrata</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	H
406	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Wettst.	Plantaginaceae	H
407	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Plumbaginaceae	H
408	<i>Acrachne racemosa</i> (B.Heyne ex Roth) Ohwi	Poaceae	H
409	<i>Alloteropsis cimicina</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
410	<i>Apluda mutica</i> L.	Poaceae	H
411	<i>Aristida adscensionis</i> L.	Poaceae	H
412	<i>Aristida setacea</i> Retz.	Poaceae	H
413	<i>Bothriochloa pertusa</i> (L.) A.Camus	Poaceae	H
414	<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
415	<i>Brachiaria eruciformis</i> (Sm.) Griseb.	Poaceae	H
416	<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
417	<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
418	<i>Brachiaria reptans</i> (L.) C.A.Gardner & C.E.Hubb.	Poaceae	H
419	<i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i> L.	Poaceae	H
420	<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	Poaceae	H
421	<i>Chrysopogon fulvus</i> (Spreng.) Chiov.	Poaceae	H
422	<i>Cymbopogon caesius</i> (Hook. & Arn.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
423	<i>Cymbopogon coloratus</i> (Hook.f.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
424	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	H
425	<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Willd	Poaceae	H
426	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> Schrad. ex J.C.Wendl.	Poaceae	H
427	<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
428	<i>Digitaria bicornis</i> (Lam.) Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
429	<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koeler	Poaceae	H
430	<i>Digitaria tomentosa</i> (J.Koenig ex Rottler) Henrard	Poaceae	H
431	<i>Dinebra retroflexa</i> (Vahl) Panz.	Poaceae	H
432	<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	H
433	<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Poaceae	H
434	<i>Enteropogon dolichostachyus</i> (Lag.) Keng	Poaceae	H
435	<i>Eragrostiella bifaria</i> (Vahl) Bor	Poaceae	H
436	<i>Eragrostiella brachyphylla</i> (Stapf) Bor	Poaceae	H
437	<i>Eragrostis amabilis</i> (L.) Wight & Arn	Poaceae	H

438	<i>Eragrostis atrovirens</i> (Desf.) Trin. ex Steud.	Poaceae	H
439	<i>Eragrostis japonica</i> (Thunb.) Trin	Poaceae	H
440	<i>Eragrostis viscosa</i> (Retz.) Trin.	Poaceae	H
441	<i>Eriochloa procera</i> (Retz.) C.E.Hubb.	Poaceae	H
442	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
443	<i>Iseilema laxum</i> Hack.	Poaceae	H
444	<i>Melanocenchris jacquemontii</i> Jaub. & Spach	Poaceae	H
445	<i>Oplismenus burmanni</i> (Retz.) P. Beauv	Poaceae	H
446	<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	H
447	<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	H
448	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Poaceae	H
449	<i>Perotis indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Poaceae	H
450	<i>Setaria intermedia</i> Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
451	<i>Setaria pumila</i> (Poir.) Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
452	<i>Setaria verticillata</i> (L.) P.Beauv.	Poaceae	H
453	<i>Sporobolus coromandelianus</i> (Retz.) Kunth	Poaceae	H
454	<i>Tetrapogon tenellus</i> (Roxb.) Chiov	Poaceae	H
455	<i>Tragus mongolorum</i> Ohwi	Poaceae	H
456	<i>Urochloa panicoides</i> P.Beauv.	Poaceae	H
457	<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i> (L.) Nash.	Poaceae	H
458	<i>Polygala arvensis</i> Willd.	Polygalaceae	H
459	<i>Polygala chinensis</i> L.	Polygalaceae	H
460	<i>Polygala elongata</i> Klein ex Willd.	Polygalaceae	H
461	<i>Polygala erioptera</i> DC	Polygalaceae	H
462	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	Portulacaceae	H
463	<i>Portulaca quadrifida</i> L.	Portulacaceae	H
464	<i>Portulaca tuberosa</i> Roxb.	Portulacaceae	H
465	<i>Actiniopteris radiata</i> (Sw.) Link	Pteridaceae	H
466	<i>Adiantum caudatum</i> L.	Pteridaceae	H
467	<i>Scutia myrtina</i> (Burm.f.) Kurz	Rhamnaceae	S
468	<i>Ventilago maderaspatana</i> Gaertn	Rhamnaceae	C
469	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> Mill	Rhamnaceae	T
470	<i>Ziziphus oenopolia</i> (L.) Mill	Rhamnaceae	S
471	<i>Ziziphus rugosa</i> Lam	Rhamnaceae	T
472	<i>Ziziphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Willd.	Rhamnaceae	T
473	<i>Benkara malabarica</i> (Lam.) Tirveng	Rubiaceae	S
474	<i>Canthium coromandelicum</i> (Burm.f.) Alston	Rubiaceae	S
475	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i> (Thunb.) Tirveng.	Rubiaceae	S
476	<i>Deccania pubescens</i> (Roth) Tirveng.	Rubiaceae	T
477	<i>Gardenia gummifera</i> L.f.	Rubiaceae	T
478	<i>Ixora pavetta</i> Andr	Rubiaceae	T
479	<i>Kohautia aspera</i> (B.Heyne ex Roth) Bremek	Rubiaceae	H
480	<i>Mitragyna parvifolia</i> (Roxb.) Korth.	Rubiaceae	T

481	<i>Morinda pubescens</i> Sm.	Rubiaceae	T
482	<i>Oldenlandia affinis</i> (Roem. & Schult.) DC	Rubiaceae	H
483	<i>Oldenlandia corymbosa</i> L.	Rubiaceae	H
484	<i>Oldenlandia herbacea</i> (L.) Roxb	Rubiaceae	H
485	<i>Oldenlandia umbellata</i> L.	Rubiaceae	H
486	<i>Pavetta indica</i> L.	Rubiaceae	T
487	<i>Psydrax dicoccos</i> Gaertn.	Rubiaceae	T
488	<i>Spermacoce articularis</i> L.f.	Rubiaceae	H
489	<i>Spermacoce pusilla</i> Wall.	Rubiaceae	H
490	<i>Tarenna asiatica</i> (L.) Kuntze ex K.Schum.	Rubiaceae	S
491	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corrêa	Rutaceae	T
492	<i>Atalantia monophylla</i> DC	Rutaceae	T
493	<i>Chloroxylon swietenia</i> DC.	Rutaceae	T
494	<i>Limonia acidissima</i> Groff	Rutaceae	T
495	<i>Murraya paniculata</i> (L.) Jack	Rutaceae	T
496	<i>Naringi crenulata</i> (Roxb.) Nicolson	Rutaceae	T
497	<i>Toddalia asiatica</i> (L.) Lam	Rutaceae	S
498	<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm.f.) Merr	Salicaceae	T
499	<i>Cardiospermum corundum</i> L.	Sapindaceae	C
500	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Sapindaceae	C
501	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (L.) Jacq.	Sapindaceae	S
502	<i>Sapindus emarginatus</i> Vahl	Sapindaceae	T
503	<i>Manilkara hexandra</i> (Roxb.) Dubard	Sapotaceae	T
504	<i>Mimusops elengi</i> L.	Sapotaceae	T
505	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb	Simaroubaceae	T
506	<i>Datura innoxia</i> Mill.	Solanaceae	S
507	<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	Solanaceae	H
508	<i>Solanum anguivi</i> Lam	Solanaceae	S
509	<i>Solanum incanum</i> L.	Solanaceae	S
510	<i>Solanum pubescens</i> Willd.	Solanaceae	S
511	<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm. f.	Solanaceae	H
512	<i>Solanum trilobatum</i> L.	Solanaceae	S
513	<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	Typhaceae	Aq.H
514	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Verbenaceae	S
515	<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	Verbenaceae	H
516	<i>Pigea enneasperma</i> (L.) P.I. Forst. (= <i>Hybanthus enneaspermus</i> (L.) F.Muell.)	Violaceae	H
517	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	Vitaceae	V
518	<i>Cissus vitiginea</i> L.	Vitaceae	C
519	<i>Cyphostemma setosum</i> (Roxb.) Alston	Vitaceae	C
520	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L.	Zygophyllaceae	H
521	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i> (L.) Delile	Zygophyllaceae	T

Note: T – Tree; S – Shrub; C – Climber; V – Vine; H – Herb.

Barleria cristata

Barleria longiflora

Barleria prionitis

Dipteracanthus prostratus

Ecbolium viride

Elytraria acaulis

Andrographis echioides

Rostellularia procumbens

Lepidagathis cristata

Rostellularia prostrata

Rungia repens

Trianthema portulacastrum

Zaleya decandra

Achyranthes aspera

Aerva javanica

Aerva lanata

Allmania nodiflora

Alternanthera pungens

Dolichandrone falcata

Coldenia procumbens

Cordia dichotoma

Ehretia microphylla

Heliotropium indicum

Trichodesma indicum

Trichodesma zeylanicum

Boswellia serrata

Garuga pinnata

Ipomoea obscura

Merremia gangetica

Merremia tridentata

Operculina turpethum

Rivea hypocrateriformis

Ctenolepis garcini

Mukia maderaspatana

Cyperus iria

Fimbristylis cymosa

Tiliacora racemosa

Tinospora sinensis

Glinus oppositifolius

Mollugo nudicaulis

Ficus hispida

F. racemosa

Syzygium cumini

Boerhavia erecta

Olax scandens

